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शोधपत्र भेजने हेतु नियम:-शोधपत्र हिन्दी या अंग्रेजी भाषा में E-mail:adhikara2z@gmail.com पर भेज सकते हैं। हिन्दी, कृतिदेव-10 में तथा अंग्रेजी, न्यू-रोमन में होना चाहिए। शोधपत्र सारगर्भित अधिकतम शब्द सीमा 2500 शब्द या लगभग 10 पेज में होना चाहिए। शोधपत्र के अन्त में शोधार्थी का नाम, मोबाईल नं0, ई-मेल सहित पूरा पता लिखा होना चाहिए। सहयोग राशि प्रत्येक शोधपत्र के लिए SBI DD 1500/-"Mukesh Kumar Malviya, Varanasi" के नाम से बनवायें। अधिक जानकारी के लिए प्रधान संपादक से संपर्क करें।

शर्त:-1.शोध-पत्रिका में समस्त पद अवैतनिक हैं। सभी रचनाओं एवं शोधों में विचार लेखकों के हैं; अतः उनके विचार से संपादक मंडल या शोध-पत्रिका का सहमत होना आवश्यक नहीं है। इस शोध-पत्रिका के प्रकाशन, संपादन, एवं मुद्रण में पूर्णतः सावधानी बरती गई है। किसी भी प्रकार की त्रुटि महज मानवीय भूल मानी जाये। त्रुटि हेतु संपादक, मुद्रक जिम्मेदार नहीं होंगे। किसी भी विवाद का क्षेत्राधिकार न्यायालय, छिन्दवाड़ा (म.प्र.) होगा।

2.स्वत्वाधिकारी, मुद्रण, प्रकाशन, संपादक द्वारा चाँद, जिला-छिन्दवाड़ा से प्रकाशित एवं सूर्या बुक एण्ड फार्म कम्प्यूटर सेन्टर, लंका, बी0एच0यू0, वाराणसी से मुद्रित।

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Mahamana's Revolutionary Vision for the Evolution of Modern Science & Technology with the Help of Vedic Knowledge

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ABSTRACT

The vision of Malaviya ji was so perfect and dynamic that every solution regarding the problems of higher education is there in one campus BHU. He also told many times that many scientific principles already mention in Veda. He believes that modern science and technology became beneficiary having no side effects if it follows Veda, Upanishads & Samhitas. He wants a campus where students from different areas work together for the betterment of society. The motive of Malaviyajji was to make higher education answerable in any condition, period. So this was the globalized vision and religious thought of Malaviyajji to enhance higher education in the global scenario.

Keywords: Vidyarthi, Veda, Upanishads, Samhita, Markandeya Purana, Yajurveda

INTRODUCTION

Pandit Madan Mohan Malaviya, also called Mahamana, (born December 25, 1861, Allahabad, India—died November 12, 1946, Allahabad), Indian scholar, educational reformer, and a leader of the Indian nationalist movement. Malaviya was the son of Pandit Brij Nath, a noted Sanskrit scholar, and his early education took place at two Sanskrit pathshalas (traditional schools). Malaviya, who was keenly interested in uplifting the educational standards of the country, was the principal founder in 1916 of the Banaras Hindu University in Varanasi, a premier institution of learning in India. He served as the university's vice-chancellor for some two decades (1919–38) and remained active at the school until his death. This great Indian scholar, educational reformer, Mahamana Malaviya's visions, perceptions, thoughts have been discussed in the next sections shortly and pointedly.

1. MAHAMANA'S VISION ON EDUCATION SYSTEM

Mahamana considered education to be the most powerful tool for the progress of Bharat. He believed that the illiteracy of Bharatiyas is due to the socio-cultural and political-economic decline of Bharat. According to him, education is the only means to alleviate the country's plight. Therefore, he spent a more important part of his life in education. Only intellectual development is not the goal of true education. Real education in Mahamana's view, aims at all-round development of human life. In his view, education is that which can develop the physical, intellectual, mental, and emotional aspects of the Vidyarthi. He wanted to make education the power to awaken the nation so that the new generation can serve the society and the nation with a selfless spirit. Malviya Ji wanted to develop a sense of service and virtue in Vidyarthi from the very beginning [1].

Fig 1 Mahamana Pandit Madan Mohan Malaviya [1]

2. EDUCATION FOR CHARACTER DEVELOPMENT

He considered the development of character to be more important than the intellectual and professional development for the growth of the person and the progress of the nation. Thus Mahamana set a very broad objective of education. He wanted to create a patriotic, virtuous, characterful, self-dependent Bharatiya citizen through education [2]. His philosophies on the education system have been described below.

3.1 Physical Education

Physical development is another important idea of Mahamana as he believed that a person with a weak body cannot be a part of the society aimed at building a strong nation. According to him, an important objective of the education system is physical development [3]. In the article titled "Mera Bachpan", Mahamana wrote extensively about three pillars of health, that is "Aahar, Shayan and Brahmacharya". He also favoured regular physical exercise, Yogasanas, and Pranayama for strengthening the body.

3.2 Education of women

Education of women is another core value of Mahamana's educational philosophy. Even, he considered the education for women more important than the education of men. The idea of Mahamana Ji was that on the basis of a national program, women should have the opportunity to read and understand the better aspects of ancient and modern cultures. According to him, the women should have been so strong that they could play an important role in the reconstruction of Bharat [4].

3.3 Banaras Hindu University - A Visionary and dreamed Education Hub of Mahamana

The founder of Banaras Hindu University, the great visionary Bharat Ratna Mahamana Pt. Madan Mohan Malviya used to believe that our tradition has acquired an enormous amount of knowledge and we should explore that knowledge for our development. Malaviya was a firm believer in ancient Indian culture and tradition and also most modern then ultra-modern in his future vision for higher education [5]. Malaviya yet born after the Macaulay period but he knew about his views, so he, again and again, said reshape the education system in all spheres bringing back our ancient education practices and moral as well as spiritual values. His vision is seen in BHU to promote learning and research generally in arts and science in all branches. To advance and diffuse such scientific, technical & professional knowledge, combined with the necessary practical training as is best calculated to help in promoting indigenous industries & in developing the material resources of the country. So these objectives show Malaviya Vision on higher education i.e. on one side reflect Veda, Upanishad, all ancient scriptures & text & on other side reflect science technology integration of medical engineering agriculture & technical education. For the first time in India, he established departments for mechanical and electrical engineering, glass technology, pharmaceutical chemistry, mining and metallurgy, chemical engineering as well as Sanskrit and Ayurveda, apart from many other courses which existed in other institutions in India. In service of the nation, Malaviya vision was to link the heritage of ancient knowledge with modern development of science and technology. He pleaded for wholehearted cooperation in building a modern Nalanda and modern Takshashila in Kashi with a blend of the best of the East and with the best of the West. While he was proud of Oxford and Cambridge with their centuries-old traditions, he was also proud of his university. He believes that the basis for any scientific discoveries and inventions is to explore, observe, experiment, and interpret. For this, one needs to bank on prior knowledge, facts that are documented, so that the results lead to new or improved status in the given realm [6].

Figure.2: Large Size Statue of Malviya on a pedestal gate, Unveiled by S. Radhakrishnan on 25 Dec 1961[6]

3. VEDA- THE OCEAN KNOWLEDGEHUB

Mahamana was very much inspired by one of the oldest and largest holy book “Veda” in which deepest knowledge could be found out. The word “Veda” means knowledge and is the most sacred scriptures of Hinduism. The Vedas are also called Sruti or Shruti (Sanskrit:श्रुति) meaning that was heard and revealed to the Sem and ascetics. The Vedas are also considered to be uncreated, eternal and exists as sound syllables. The Vedas contain hymns, incantations, and rituals. Apart from their spiritual values, they provide mankind with values for everyday life. The most holy hymns and mantras have been put together into four collections and these are called the Rig-Veda, Sama-Veda, Yajur-Veda, and Atharva-Veda. The four Vedas contain information on many aspects of arts, crafts, science, and engineering. The Vedas cover all fields of knowledge both material and spiritual [7].

Few have mentioned below.

- 1) Artha-Veda-dealing with statecraft
- 2) Ayur-Veda-concerns medicine and health
- 3) Dhanur-Veda-discusses military science
- 4) Gandhrva-Veda-unfolds music and arts
- 5) Sthapatya-Veda-explains architecture

4. MAHAMANA’S VISION ON SCIENCE , TECHNOLOGY AND VEDA

Mahamana focused on providing ancient as well as modern education in the forms of ancient Bharatiya culture, philosophy, literature and history, the teaching of Veda-Vedang and Sanskrit literature, the study of modern science, electronics engineering, metallurgy, mining work, agricultural science, humanities, social science and sciences including medical science, Ayurveda and Astronomy, etc. He wants to connect science and technology with our traditional subject so he made one campus for the entire subjects. Malviya Ji was not happy with English educational policy for India mainly because it was for the destruction of Indian culture and civilization. It is in this context that Vedas, which are the primary texts of Hinduism, assume great importance [7].

Fig.3: Oldest Manuscripts of Veda [7]

It is also true that ancient Rishis' proved the various scientific theories based totally on Vedic engineering for more than thousands of years ago. In Vedic literature, there are so many verses that specify the speculation of the universe, Medicine, Life sciences, Instrumentation, Astrology, Metallurgy, Chemistry, Telegraphy, and Engineering. We must always regretful to those great, prominent, eminent Rishis' who founded a root of knowledge in the shape of Vedas & Upanishads and scattered this expertise throughout the world. Malaviya Ji wanted to mix the Indian culture with that of the European science, which even we want today and try. There would be few such people who have such unique flames in their hearts for Indian freedom, as was in the case of Malaviya Ji. This is a big part of his life-Our Culture, Ancient Culture, and combining it with today's world. Among the big leaders, Malaviya Ji had a strong attraction towards the ancient culture. It was a good thought in that period as the country was getting disoriented. It was already lost. English and English culture had influenced the Indian leaders a lot. Malaviya Ji stressed on Indian culture. He used to stop the flood of English culture, not by criticism but with his work, thoughts and tried to spread Indian culture [7].

5. MAHAMANA'S VISIONS ON MODERN ENGINEERING PRINCIPLE MENTION IN VEDA

In a straight word, it can be said that Veda is just another name that is synonyms of knowledge. It contains large of the largest, deep of deepest information which is needed in every stage of life. Hence Veda has also contributed knowledge in the field of engineering so many years ago. Mahamana was truly inspired by this information after reading Veda. The few can be discussed here[8].

6.1 In the field of electronics and instrumentation

Mahamana's derivations can be stated in a point-wise manner as

- 1) Digital electronics based on zero and one and number system mention by Brahmagupta and Aryabhata.
- 2) Communication theory (Data transmission concept by lord Narada), (Dual Mode Signal Generator or Receptor) by Sanjay in Mahabharata.
- 3) Embedded System in Veda (Lord Chitragupta – The supercomputer with high microprocessor)
- 4) Nuclear instrumentation in Veda (Brahmastra, pashupatastra)
- 5) Artificial Intelligence, Robotics, and automata in Veda describe by Yoga Vasistha.
- 6) Biomedical Instrumentation in the Vedic Period (Sushruta: 'The Father of Surgery)
- 7) Flight Instrumentation in Vedic period Vaimanika Shastra in Rig Veda.
- 8) Measurement of length, weight, colour, time and speed of sunlight is already mentioned in Veda

6.2 In the field of energy

- 1) Hydro energy, geothermal energy discussed in Yajurveda

- 2) Law of conservation of energy, Law of equivalence of mass-energy bioenergy discussed in Rig-Veda
- 3) Electrical energy discussed in Atharvaveda and Rig-Veda.

6.3 Scientific Principles mentioned in Veda

- 1) Newton 1st, 2nd, 3rd law of motion discussed in Vaisheshika Sutra (in 600 BCE).
- 2) Atomic Theory developed by Acharya Kanad (His real name was Kashyap).
- 3) Theory of gravity already discussed by Bhaskaracharya.
- 4) Atomism And Quantum Physics discussed by Acharya Kanad (His real name was Kashyap).
- 5) Blue Colour of Sky discussed in Markandeya Purana 78.8)
- 6) Earth is flattened at the poles' (Markandeya Purana 54.12)
- 7) The shape of the earth is like an Oblate Spheroid. (Rig Veda 30.4.5)

6.4 In the Field of Architectural

Veda's contribution towards the field of architecture is extremely high. The few of them are given below.

- 1) The science of Vasthu Satra
- 2) The world of Civilisation

6.5 In the Field of Mathematical Sciences

Brahmagupta (seventh century), Mahavira (ninth century) and Bhaskara (twelfth century) made several important contributions, and discoveries which were not known in Europe till renaissance.

6. CONCLUSION

Mahamana thinks that we have to advance in our technology with our religion which told us the betterment of society. Malaviya always emphasized the pattern of education that should be "a blend of worldly knowledge and spiritual wisdom" and established BHU on these bases, "Civilisation changes after few years, while the culture is everlasting. He advocates higher education by integrating both Indian culture and civilization and science and technology aiming to promote high moral value and character building on the one hand and the other, autonomy, independence, and economic prosperity among Indians. Kashi Hindu Vishwavidyalaya, popularly called Banaras Hindu University (BHU), is the creation of his soul force, which has been contributing continuously in several ways to the making of modern India. Mahamana's belief is based on all-round development and he emphasized on education and character building. The vision of Malaviya Ji was so perfect and dynamic that every solution regarding the problems of higher education is there (BHU). The motive of Malaviyaji was to make higher education answerable in any condition, period. Mahamana's view about education policy should be based on "Vedic knowledge and modern science". One Day the whole world will look towards India. Ideas of Mahamana are certainly very important for us in these times. Our cultural heritage is our strength. Based on the vision of Mahamana, Ancient knowledge should become part of every discipline.

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